

WHAT IS THE MAIN FOCUS OF THE SPEAKING FLUENTLY IN THE LANGUAGE BEING STUDIED?

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Annotation. This article discusses views on the role of grammar, vocabulary, as well as motivation and self-assurance among the students who are learning the new language. This paper is based on my research and explorations conducted by other researchers on the importance of self-confidence, concentration and motivation that has arisen on the course of teaching a language to students.

Key words: grammar, vocabulary, motivation, attitude, self-assurance, concentration.

Language is the basic means of communication. Language learning and teaching are current complex problems. Opinions on which methods are most effective in language teaching are being studied and analyzed by all researchers. There are many ways to teach and learn a language, and this article is based on an idea that emerged as a result of research and observations.

The role of grammar and vocabulary in learning language.

Grammar is the heart of the language. Grammar rules are the plans of a language. The new language learners basically focus on the grammar structure of this language. Some entrants try to study the grammar deeply, and they mark the correct answer to almost all of the questions, but during the study some of them may feel themselves like their knowledge, their comprehension are inferior to that of the others who have passed language proficiency tests. But the other students with a lack of grammatical accuracy have a fluent speech.

Vocabulary is the material of language. The spacious vocabulary plays an essential role in speaking flawlessly. The more we embrace the new words, the more we express our thoughts in this language. For instance, to speak fluently in English your vocabulary should be very wide, because the English words have at least four or five synonyms. Therefore they use various synonyms of words in their speech and teachers always advise their students to learn all of words with their synonyms.

There is the situation analysis encountered by Marianna Pascal the official trainer of the Miss Malaysia World. She talked about one of these problems in her TED talk called "Speak it like you're playing a video game." The main reason for

this is low self-confidence, poor hearing attention, that is the main focus is not on the speaker but on themselves. She reaffirmed that if we want to speak with great confidence, when we speak we shouldn't focus on ourselves, we should focus on the other person and the result we wanted to achieve.

The role of teachers, students' attitude and motivation to study hard.

Motivation is willingness to do something. It is the reason why we want to do something.

Gardner(1985) depicts the motivation as a junction of compound variables, expression of endeavours, motive and desire for L2.

The results of a survey conducted by researchers using Attitude Motivation Test Battery (AMTB) developed by Gardner (1985) among 2 groups studying at one of the universities in Indonesia were positive. They asked students twenty questions about their attitudes towards their teachers, their motivations , and their success in the language learning process.

I observed and analyzed two English teachers nurturing and teaching methods. I contemplated the students attitudes towards them. The first teacher adheres to explain one or two themes from grammar and emphasizes them to do the test based on those themes to strengthen their knowledge. The second teacher's technique is completely different frome this. Each lesson begins with listening the english song. The choice of song also requires consideration while teaching the language. She selects the song with pure pronunciation and which is appropriate to their age. Then the students are asked which places they found crucial to pronounce and then they deal with these issues. In the next step she asks them to say the synonyms for what she said. Through this way she determines how well they understand the meaning of words. The teacher also conducts a debates among the students to expand their communication skill and to determine how well their speech is progressing. But the most important thing in this lesson process is that the teacher's attitude towards the students, their motivation, is what makes the students interested in learning.

Based on those i conducted a questionnaire among four groups. I asked the „ What is the main thing that helps you to speak fluently in the language you are learning? Then i offered them three options.

According to the survey, 15 students from the first group, 14 students from the second group and 15 students from the third group participated. As shown in the table the option gained the most votes of the students is the debates. But the rest of students(46) who didn't paticipated said that their self- confidence,

their attitudes towards learning and teachers motivations play a significant role while studying.

I can say these based on my own observations and analysis teaching the students regularly grammatical structure of language doesn't provide the most basic help to improve the speaking skill. Both should be regularly increased at the same time. The main thing that helps students to learn perfectly is the motivation given them, as well as their interests, their self- assurance.

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